

SIROP

LOD-GEOSS

Open Energy Platform

Publication of FAIR Data and Metadata

Part 3: Data Publication on the Energy Databus

Ludwig Hülk

2023-03-22

© Reiner Lemoine Institut

Open Energy Family

Open Energy Family

Energy Databus

Databus aggregates metadata (including basic provenance) via external maven repositories
This information includes locations of data and provenance

Report Issue

Sparql Endpoint

API Documentation

ludee

Publish Data

This form will help you set up a Datald. A Datald is a metadata document containing important information about your files. This metadata document will make your data more understandable and reusable for you and other users.

Please fill out the form below and follow the instructions in the infoboxes. You can read the infoboxes by hovering the info icons. Also make sure to fix all errors (denoted by a red explanation mark). You can read the error description by hovering the red error icons.

GROUP INFO ⚠ i

Create New Group

Id
The group id is invalid. Please enter at least 3 characters.

Label
The group label is invalid. Please enter at least 3 characters.

Abstract
The group abstract is invalid. Please enter at least 25 characters (plain text).

- Register and Login
- “Publish Data”

<https://energy.databus.dbpedia.org/>

Databus-MOSS

Search

Annotate

Submit Metadata

Metadata Submission

Submit Metadata to a Databus File

https://databus.dbpedia.org/jj-author/mastr/bnetza-mastr/01.04.01/bnetza-mastr_rli_tyj


```
[<http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#_comment>
  [<http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#dates>
    "Dates and time must follow the ISO8601 including time zone (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss±hh)";
    <http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#languages>
      "Languages must follow the IETF (BCP47) format (en-GB, en-US, de-DE)";
    <http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#licenses>
      "License name must follow the SPDX License List (https://spdx.org/licenses/)";
    <http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#metadata>
      "Metadata documentation and explanation (https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/organisation/wiki/metadata)";
    <http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#null>
      "If not applicable use (null)";
    <http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#review>
      "Following the OEP Data Review (https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/data-preprocessing/wiki)";
    <http://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/ns/demo#units>
      "Use a space between numbers and units (100 m)"
```

- Submit metadata

<https://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/submit-data>

„The opposite of **‘open’** isn’t **‘closed’**. The opposite of **‘open’** is **‘broken’**.“

License

Except where otherwise noted, this work and its content (texts and illustrations) are licensed under the [Attribution 4.0 International \(CC-BY-4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

See license text for further information.

Please quote as:

“FAIR-Metadaten in der Energiesystemanalyse – Part 3: Data Publication on the Energy Databus (2023-03-22)” © [Reiner Lemoine Institut](https://reinerlemoineinstitut.de/) | [CC-BY-4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Ludwig Hülk

E-Mail: ludwig.huelk@rl-institut.de

Web: <http://www.rl-institut.de>

Twitter: @LudwigHuelk